

Six of the 12 hybrids showed strikingly increased survival compared to their parents (see table). In three cases, hybrids and parents were comparable; in two, hybrids were inferior to the better parent. The hybrid 97A/Milyang 54 showed superiority over the parents at early stages but subsequently became comparable to them.

These results indicate that F₁ hybrids could be superior to their parents in adaptability to salinity. Because the parents of the hybrids tested are not known for salinity tolerance, better performance of some hybrids can be attributed to increased root and shoot vigor.

Survival of some parents (female, male) and their hybrids (F₁) at 6, 12, and 15 wk after transplanting (WAT) in a saline field (EC = 7 dS/m). IRRI, 1986.

Hybrid or variety	Survival (%)								
	6 WAT			12 WAT			15 WAT		
	Female	Male	F ₁	Female	Male	F ₁	Female	Male	F ₁
97A/Milyang 54	26	32	50	16	12	16	16	10	16
IR46830A/IR50	28	58	60	8	46	54	8	40	46
IR46830A/IR9761-19-1	28	26	64	8	14	34	8	8	18
V20A/IR9761-19-1	16	26	28	16	14	18	14	8	12
IR21845/IR29512	28	74	38	18	66	22	14	62	16
IR21845/IR19392	28	48	60	18	44	54	14	44	50
IR21845/IR20933	28	22	44	18	8	40	14	8	34
IR21845/IR14753	28	28	46	18	24	40	14	24	30
IR21845/IR15847	28	22	24	18	16	18	14	12	12
IR21845/IR4422	28	36	32	18	28	24	14	20	12
IR21845/IR13146	28	38	36	18	24	28	14	24	22
IR21845/IR54 R	28	28	46	18	28	46	14	26	40
IR9884-54-3 (resistant check)		93			90			83	
IR28 (susceptible check)		42			40			33	

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

TISSUE CULTURE

Variability in quantitative traits of anther culture-derived progenies

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We studied the pattern of variability in quantitative traits of homozygous lines developed from anther-derived plants of the cross Co 37/Co 40.

Anthers were collected from F₁ plants during 1979 wet season and cultured in the laboratory. Sixteen

plants were established in October 1980. Seven A₁ plants (R1 to R7) resembling the parent (Co 37) in vigor, growth, and seed set were grown individually in A₂ in 1981 wet season (Jun-Sep). They were uniform within each progeny and carried forward as individual lines.

During 1982 wet season, 10 plants were established for each entry, with 3 replications. The F₄ of Co 37/Co 40 and Co 37 alone were included for comparison. Plant height at maturity, number of productive tillers, panicle

length, grains per panicle, and grain yield per plant were measured for each plant.

All the seven lines exhibited variations comparable to that in Co 37. The F₄ population of the cross showed perceptible variation between plants and within lines for all characters. Similar variation was observed in the next generation during 1983 dry season for all the traits except panicle length. Compared to that in the anther-derived lines, variation was high for all traits (see table).

Performance of anther-derived lines at Coimbatore, India, 1983 dry season.

Culture	Plant height (cm)			Tillers (no.)			Panicle length (cm)			Grains/panicle			Grain weight/plant (g)		
	Range	Mean ± SE	CV	Range	Mean ± SE	CV	Range	Mean ± SE	CV	Range	Mean ± SE	CV	Range	Mean ± SE	CV
433 A R1	84-98	91.5±3.9	4.9	6-11	7.9±1.6	21.4	20.1-27.1	22.6±28.0	82.7	143-167	153.5±8.3	5.6	9.0-10.0	9.6±3.1	3.2
433 A R2	84-92	89.1±2.6	3.6	5-12	8.7±2.3	27.1	19.5-23.6	21.6±13.1	62.7	95-165	130.5±20.2	15.9	8.2-9.0	8.6±2.6	3.0
433 A R3	85-98	90.8±3.7	4.1	5-12	8.3±2.2	27.4	19.5-24.3	22.4±11.9	54.7	116-228	169.1±28.3	17.3	8.1-8.8	8.5±2.3	2.8
433 A R4	83-95	88.8±3.2	3.7	5-12	8.2±1.9	24.0	21.8-24.8	23.5± 9.4	41.6	105-188	138.1±26.0	19.5	6.3-7.0	6.7±2.3	3.5
433 A R5	79-95	85.2±5.5	6.3	7-12	9.7±1.9	20.2	19.0-23.2	21.8±10.5	49.8	85-191	131.9±34.9	27.4	10.2-11.1	10.7±2.9	2.8
433 A R6	75-96	85.0±5.5	6.6	7-12	8.9±1.8	20.8	19.7-24.5	21.5±13.3	63.9	75-205	122.1±39.2	33.2	9.2-10.3	9.7±3.3	3.5
433 A R7	82-94	87.8±3.6	4.3	6-12	9.2±1.9	22.2	18.3-23.5	21.1±14.2	69.8	97-185	141.4±30.0	21.9	9.0-9.9	9.5±3.0	3.2
Vaigai (Co 37)	94-119	103.5±6.4	6.4	5-12	7.9±2.1	27.9	21.4-24.4	22.7±12.8	38.3	100-160	129.7±17.3	14.2	8.4-9.2	8.8±2.5	2.9
Vaigai/Co 40 (F5)	90-138	116.2±7.4	7.8	6-12	9.6±2.1	30.2	20.1-27.2	23.4±16.2	72.4	77-175	127.7±27.0	26.8	8.1-13.4	10.6±5.0	5.7

Duration of the anther-derived progenies was 135 d; it was 120 d in Co 37.

Homozygosity for quantitative traits

in anther-derived plants in the A₂ generation was manifest and stabilization in the immediate generation was exhibited in the

diploidized haploids developed through anther culture. These lines are being tested for yield performance. □

Pest Control and Management

DISEASES

Virulence of isolates of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* of Haryana

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Twenty-four isolates of the bacterial blight (BB) pathogen *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* collected from rice growing areas of Haryana State (12 from Karnal, 4 from Kurukshetra, and 8 from Ambala District) were tested Jul-Aug 1985 in the screenhouse on 8 differential hosts. Inoculations were made at maximum tillering stage by the clipping technique using a single-colony culture of bacterial suspension (10 D at 600 nm) isolated from samples taken from different locations.

Disease reaction was assessed by lesion length: 0.0-3.0 cm = resistant, 3.1-6.0 cm = moderately resistant, 6.1-9.0 cm = moderately susceptible, 9.1-12.0 cm = susceptible, and 12.1 cm or longer = highly susceptible. Lesion development on 9 randomly collected inoculated leaves was high 15 d after inoculation (see table).

Virulence of isolates varied considerably. TN1, with no known major resistance gene, had a susceptible reaction to all the isolates. BJ1 displayed the broadest resistance. One isolate was virulent on BJ1, three on Zenith, four on TKM6 and Sigadis, five on IET4141, and seven each on IR36 and DV85.

A difference of one grade was used to divide differential isolate-variety interaction into 9 groups (I has isolates 1, 8-16, 18, 19, 22, and 24; II has

Reaction of isolates of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* on rice differential hosts. Haryana, India, 1985.

Isolate no.	Reaction ^a							
	TN1	TKM6	Sigadis	IR36	IET4141	BJ1	DV85	Zenith
	<i>Karnal</i>							
1	MS	MR	R	MR	MR	R	R	R
2	S	MR	MR	MS	MS	MS	MS	MR
3	HS	HS	MS	S	HS	R	HS	MR
4	S	HS	MS	S	MS	MR	MR	S
5	HS	R	MS	MR	MR	R	MS	MR
6	HS	MR	R	S	MS	R	HS	S
7	HS	R	MR	MS	MR	R	S	MR
8	S	R	R	MR	MR	R	R	R
9	MS	R	R	R	MR	R	R	R
10	HS	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
11	MS	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
12	MS	R	MR	R	R	R	R	R
	<i>Kurukshetra</i>							
13	MS	R	MR	R	R	R	R	MR
14	MS	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
15	MS	R	MR	R	R	R	R	R
16	MS	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
	<i>Ambala</i>							
17	S	R	MS	R	MR	R	R	R
18	MS	R	R	R	MR	R	MR	R
19	MS	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
20	S	MS	MR	MR	MR	R	MR	MS
21	HS	MR	MR	MS	MR	R	MS	MR
22	S	MR	R	R	R	R	R	MR
23	HS	MS	R	S	MS	R	MS	MR
24	S	R	MR	MR	R	R	R	R

^aR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible, HS = highly susceptible.

isolate 2; III, 3; IV, 4; V, 5, 7, and 21; VI, 6; VII, 17; VIII, 20; and IX, 23). Group I is weakly virulent; groups II, V, VII, VIII, and IX are moderately virulent; and groups III, IV, and VI are highly virulent. These results show that more than one pathotype of *X. campestris* pv. *oryzae* has developed in Haryana.

The variation in rice differentials-bacterium interaction might have several explanations. All the major genes in the rice differentials from Japan or from the Philippines were identified by using domestic bacterial

isolates, which cannot be expected to show identical reactions with isolates of another country. The major genes in the rice differential genotypes were from different genetic backgrounds and could vary in their expression. An isogenic set of differentials is the only way to rule out this variation. Rice varieties could have horizontal resistance governed by polygenes. The variation in lesion length in these differentials could be explained by the existence of such horizontal resistance. □